

Developing a Wellbeing Lens for Researchers

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Purpose

The purpose of this presentation is to analyse the development and applications of a tool to support the development of knowledge, behaviours and attributes that contribute to positive wellbeing and mental health for researchers. The Wellbeing and Mental Health Lens is one of a series of lenses on the Vitae Researcher Development Framework (RDF), a framework which was developed with researchers working in the higher education sector to support the planning, promotion and enhancement of professional development. The development of the lens was prompted by research undertaken in the UK which identified issues in the wellbeing and mental health of the postgraduate researcher culture and in research culture more widely. Within the wider context, the Postgraduate Researcher Experience Survey (2019) showed that the wellbeing levels of postgraduate researchers are below that of the general population and that anxiety is significantly higher than that of the undergraduate population. Moreover, a report commissioned by Wellcome (2020) indicated that poor research culture is leading to stress, anxiety and mental health problems. Both reports highlight a need to focus on strategies to support researchers and institutions for the promotion of good wellbeing and mental health within professional development and training.

Design

There are a number of lenses which have been created for the RDF to enable researchers to strategically align their professional development and training to specific areas of priority. Examples include: employability, intellectual property, teaching and information literacy. The impetus for the creation of this lens was work undertaken by a UK University as part of an Office for Students funded project to integrate the wellbeing and mental health of postgraduate researchers into the graduate school development and supervisor training programmes. It has been co-created with the UK researcher development community through

iterative engagement and consultation of sector experts to reflect the breadth and depth of different institutional contexts across the research landscape.

The lens selects 19 of 63 descriptors in the RDF which the engagement and consultation process identified as being the most important in supporting individual researchers and contributing to the creation of a mentally healthy environment and research culture. The lens can be used by individual researchers to: (1) identify how the skills and attributes they have developed underpin their development in relation to wellbeing and mental health; (2) select areas that they want to develop to build good wellbeing and mental health; (3) to provide a language to evidence the transferability of their skills and attributes in relation to wellbeing and mental health. At an institutional level, the lens can demonstrate to researchers and other stakeholders: (1) how good wellbeing and mental health can contribute towards the overall professional development of researchers; (2) align existing resources professional development provision to promote positive wellbeing practices; (3) provide a framework against which researchers, supervisors and research developers can measure institutional practices and commitments.

Results

There are a number of different ways in which universities have used the RDF framework to enhance researcher development, for example using the framework to facilitate skills needs analyses for doctoral students. Students can identify areas of development and create action plans to address them. In some cases, this may be used as an induction activity, or to inform reviews of progress, or to assist students in selecting appropriate professional development activities. For example a UK University has used it to inform its programme for new academic staff, requiring staff to complete a Professional Development Plan (PDP) mapped to the RDF and planning actions and targets to achieve and enhance existing attributes. It concluded that this process could be used for teaching-only staff to develop and expand their role (Bray & Boon, 2011). However, there has been less attention paid to how the RDF different lenses can be used and this presentation will explore some specific suggestions about how the Wellbeing RDF lens can be incorporated into strategies for improving research culture within institutions.

Implications

The Wellbeing lens provides a useful tool that can be used to support the aims and objectives of the REMO Researcher Mental Health and Wellbeing Manifesto. At the micro level, it can support a person-centred approach to training and career management, enabling researchers to explicitly align their activities to support and promote good mental health and wellbeing. At the meso level, it enables wellbeing to be explicitly addressed in the development of programmes to support staff and supervisors. The co-created nature of the lens through engagement and consultation with key stakeholders also promotes ownership of the resources by researchers and empowers them to contribute to the improvement of research culture within their own spheres of influence.

Acknowledgments

Bray, R. and Boon, S. (2011), “Towards a framework for research career development”,
International Journal for Researcher Development, Vol. 2 No. 2, pp. 99-116.

<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/17597511111212709/full/html>

Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers

<https://researcherdevelopmentconcordat.ac.uk/>

Williams, S. Postgraduate Research Experience Survey 2019

<https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/knowledge-hub/postgraduate-research-experience-survey-2019>

Wellcome (2020) What researchers think about the culture they work in

<https://wellcome.org/reports/what-researchers-think-about-research-culture>

Resources

Lenses on the Vitae Researcher Development Framework

<https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework/lenses-on-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework>

About the Vitae Researcher Development Framework

<https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework>

Wellbeing and mental health lens

<https://www.vitae.ac.uk/vitae-publications/rdf-related/wellbeing-and-mental-health-lens/view>